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Final test report:

- Data analysis of the temperatures measured inside a gas burner
 - Test bench setup for a micro-cogeneration system

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Abstract

This thesis presents two studies aimed at improving experimental understanding and performance evaluation of thermal systems.

The first part focuses on the statistical analysis of temperature measurements inside a gas burner. A detailed calibration of type-B thermocouples was conducted, followed by data acquisition with 1,600 and 10,000 samples. Statistical and critical analyses were performed to assess measurement uncertainty and the influence of sample size. Radiative losses were also estimated to refine the determination of the true gas temperature.

The second part describes the design and setup of a test bench for a micro-cogeneration system. The test bench allows the simultaneous measurement of thermal and electrical outputs, fuel consumption, and exhaust composition. Using these data, the main performance indicators were determined: thermal efficiency of 89.3%, electrical efficiency of 10.1%, and a Primary Energy Saving (PES) index of 0.17, meeting EU high-efficiency cogeneration standards. Emission analyses showed significantly reduced NO_x levels compared to conventional boilers.

The developed test bench proved to be accurate and reliable, with measurement uncertainties comparable to existing laboratory systems, and can be used for future evaluations of similar cogeneration technologies.

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1. Data analysis of the measured temperature inside a gas burner

1.1. Statistical analysis

Two samplings (1600 and 10,000 samples, respectively) of the burner temperature measurement were performed.

The statistical analysis is then performed, including data classification, histogram construction, calculation of the mean value and standard deviation, and estimation of the statistical error. Finally, a critical analysis of the possible influence of the number of samples on the results of this statistical inference is discussed.

The sampling was performed with the following parameters:

$$\text{sampling rate} = f_c = 100 \text{ Hz}$$

$$\text{sampling interval} = \frac{1}{f_c} = 0.01 \text{ s}$$

1.1.1. Static thermocouple calibration

To estimate the systematic error of the thermocouple, it is necessary to static calibrate it. To this end, the static calibration table for a type B thermocouple is obtained from the supplier's datasheet.

Tensione [mV]	Temperatura misurata tramite strumento campione [°C]
0,786	400
1,791	600
2,431	700
2,784	750
3,158	800
3,551	850
3,963	900

4,395	950
4,844	1000
5,311	1050
5,793	1100
6,29	1150
6,8	1200
7,326	1250
7,866	1300
8,418	1350
8,979	1400
9,549	1450
10,124	1500
10,704	1550
11,286	1600

From this data, using linear regression, it is derived the relationship between input (temperature value) and output (voltage value) characteristic of our instrument. The following graph illustrates this linear relationship:

Regressione lineare della termocoppia ottenuta tramite i dati disponibili

The data of fundamental importance for the characterization of the instrument are the following:

$$\text{Static sensitivity } (m) = 0.00923 \frac{\text{mV}}{^{\circ}\text{C}}$$

$$\text{Known term (intercept)}(q) = -4.03345 \text{ mV}$$

These last two data, as can be seen from the equation shown in the graph, are the coefficients of the linear regression equation.

$$\text{Linearity standard deviation } (S_{l,out}) = \sqrt{\frac{SQ}{p-2}} = 0.38752 \text{ mV}$$

Where:

- p is the number of points ($p=21$), from which the points fixed to perform the regression are subtracted (in the linear case they are 2),
- SQ represents the sum of the squared distances between the calibration points and the corresponding points on the regression line with the same x-coordinate.

$$SQ = \sum_{i=1}^p [y_i - (mx_i + q)]^2$$

The linearity standard deviation ($S_{l,out}$) also represents the standard uncertainty related to the instrument's linearity and therefore to the systematic error. It is useful to know the

instrument's uncertainty in input measurement units. To do this, simply divide the linearity standard deviation by the instrument's sensitivity.

$$\text{Linearity standard deviation in } ^\circ\text{C } (S_l) = \frac{S_{l,out}[mV]}{m[\frac{mV}{^\circ\text{C}}]} = 41.98^\circ\text{C}$$

However, it is clear that the standard deviation obtained is quite high. Furthermore, from the graph, it is visible that the linear regression line does not approximate the obtained data very well. Indeed, it is useful to note from the residuals graph how they are dispersed in a non-optimal way, a symptom of the poor quality of the approximation.

Grafico dei residui

At this point, it's appropriate to perform a polynomial regression, which will obviously be able to simulate the thermocouple's behavior much better based on the available data. A good compromise is offered by a degree-four polynomial regression, the graph of which is shown below:

Regressione polinomiale di grado 4

To confirm the reliability of this approximation it is useful to observe how the residues are very small and rather uniformly distributed:

Grafico dei residui

The main problem with using polynomial regression is defining uncertainty. It is, in fact, a function of temperature, since from the formula defined previously:

$$\text{Linearity standard deviation in } ^\circ\text{C} (S_l) = \frac{S_{l,out} [mV]}{m [\frac{mV}{^\circ\text{C}}]}$$

Where m is the sensitivity and is calculated as:

$$m = \left| \frac{dy}{dx} \right|$$

It is easy to note that in the case of linear regression (of degree 1), m will be equal to a constant, and therefore the transition from the linearity standard deviation in output units ($S_{l,out} [mV]$) to the one in input units ($S_l [^\circ\text{C}]$) is immediate. However, in the case of polynomial regression (of degree >1), m will be a function of x , consequently the linearity standard deviation defined in input units ($S_l [^\circ\text{C}]$) will also depend on temperature.

What has just been said is highlighted here, using the data at our disposal obtained from the polynomial regression. The regression function from Figure 3, is:

$$f(x) = -3.6206 \cdot 10^{-13} x^4 + 3.1396 \cdot 10^{-13} x^3 + 4.6785 \cdot 10^{-6} x^2 + 3.1117 \cdot 10^{-4} x - 9.8704 \cdot 10^{-2}$$

The sensitivity m is then defined:

$$m = \left| \frac{dy}{dx} \right| = 1.4823 \cdot 10^{-12} x^3 + 9.4189 \cdot 10^{-10} x^2 + 9.357 \cdot 10^{-6} x + 3.1117 \cdot 10^{-4}$$

The standard deviation of linearity is calculated similarly to linear regression:

$$S_{l,out} = \sqrt{\frac{SQ}{p-5}} = 0.00223467 \text{ mV}$$

Where, in this case, the points fixed to perform the regression (of degree 4) are 5, and SQ is the sum of the squares of the distances between the points found during the calibration and those on the regression polynomial having the same abscissa:

$$SQ = \sum_{i=1}^p [y_i - f(x_i)]^2 = 7.99 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mV}^2$$

Possiamo ora scrivere lo scarto tipo di linearità in $^\circ\text{C}$, che per quanto detto prima sarà pari a:

$$S_l = \frac{S_{l,out} [mV]}{m [\frac{mV}{^\circ\text{C}}]} = \frac{0,00223467}{1.4823 \cdot 10^{-12} x^3 + 9.4189 \cdot 10^{-10} x^2 + 9.357 \cdot 10^{-6} x + 3.1117 \cdot 10^{-4}}$$

Which, as anticipated, is a function of the temperature (x). In particular, S_l is inversely proportional to the square of the temperature, in fact considering that the slope of the regression function $f(x)$ increases with the cubic power of the temperature, it is intuitive to think that the uncertainty in the temperature itself decreases as it moves towards higher values. This reasoning can be better understood by observing the graph of S_l :

In summary, linear regression does not optimally fit the data provided by the manufacturer, thus providing too much data uncertainty. Polynomial regression, on the other hand, simulates the thermocouple's operation very well, but has the major drawback of providing uncertainty as a function of temperature, making it a parameter that is difficult to use in statistical analysis or would lead to excessive complications.

If it was only needed to calibrate the thermocouple alone, it would clearly be appropriate to use polynomial regression. However, since it is useful to know the systematic error for statistical analysis of the burner measurements, it is better to take a different approach.

For statistical analysis purposes only, it is appropriate to extrapolate from the manufacturer's data only the temperature values of interest, i.e., 900-1500°C, in order to construct a linear regression based solely on these data, which will certainly perform better than the previous one. Indeed, it is possible to note from the graph that the data in the range of interest are fairly linearly distributed.

Regressione lineare ottenuta con i dati della tabella 1

The data characterizing the behavior of the instrument in the range 900-1500 °C, obtainable from linear regression are:

$$\text{Static sensitivity } (m) = 0.01030 \left[\frac{mV}{^{\circ}C} \right]$$

$$\text{Known term (intercept)}(q) = - 5.46969 \text{ [mV]}$$

$$\text{Linearity standard deviation } (S_{l,out}) = \sqrt{\frac{SQ}{p-2}} = 0.09126 \text{ mV}$$

Where SQ, as previously stated, is:

$$SQ = \sum_{i=1}^p [y_i - (mx_i + q)]^2$$

As already stated, the linearity standard deviation (S_l) also represents the standard uncertainty related to the linearity of the instrument and therefore to the systematic error. It is necessary to define the standard deviation in temperature units:

$$S_l = \frac{S_{l,out} [mV]}{m \left[\frac{mV}{^{\circ}C} \right]} = 8.86^{\circ}C$$

This is the instrumental uncertainty which will be useful for the purposes of statistical analysis and for defining the measurement of the gas temperature inside the burner.

1.1.2. Analysis of data from the collection of 1600 samples

$$\text{Mean value } (\bar{x}) = \frac{\sum T_i}{n} = 1082.84958 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

$$\text{Standard deviation } (S) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}} = 39.14723 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

$$\text{Standard error of the mean} = S_x = \frac{S}{\sqrt{n}} = 0.97868 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

It is known that temperature measurement is affected by two types of uncertainty: one related to systematic error (characteristic of the thermocouple used) and one related to statistical error (related to the repetition of 1600 measurements). It is therefore appropriate to define the total error by combining the uncertainties:

$$\varepsilon_{tot} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{syst}^2 + \varepsilon_{stat}^2} = \sqrt{S_l^2 + S_x^2} = 8.91 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

It is now possible to define the measurement of temperature:

$$T_{68\%} = 1082.8 \pm 8.9 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

This measurement has a 68% confidence level, meaning that the actual temperature value will fall within the interval with a 68% probability.

To extend the confidence interval, multiply the standard deviation by the Student t-coverage factor (K). If the data collection contains a sufficiently large number of samples, as in our case, a coverage factor of K=2 can be used to extend the confidence level to 95%:

$$\varepsilon_{tot} \cdot K = 17.8^{\circ}\text{C}$$

Therefore:

$$T_{95\%} = 1082.8 \pm 17,8^{\circ}\text{C}$$

1.1.3. Analysis of data from the collection of 10000 samples

Istogramma dei valori delle misure di temperatura sul bruciatore

$$\text{Mean value } (\bar{x}) = \frac{\sum T_i}{n} = 1159.16884^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$\text{Standard deviation } (S) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}} = 77.84111^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$\text{Standard error of the mean} = S_x = \frac{S}{\sqrt{n}} = 0.77841^{\circ}\text{C}$$

As previously done, the total uncertainty is calculated, due to both systematic and statistical errors.

$$\varepsilon_{tot} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{syst}^2 + \varepsilon_{stat}^2} = \sqrt{S_l^2 + S_x^2} = 8.89 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

The temperature measurement is, therefore, defined as:

$$T_{68\%} = 1082.8 \pm 8.9 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

As before, the standard deviation is multiplied by the coverage factor $K=2$, to obtain a 95% confidence interval.

$$\varepsilon_{tot} \cdot K = 17.8 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

Therefore:

$$T_{95\%} = 1159.2 \pm 17.8 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

1.2. Critical analysis

It's interesting to make some observations about the recently completed statistical analysis.

First, the uncertainty is equal in both cases. This is due to the fact that, due to the large number of samples present in each measurement, the systematic error is much higher than the statistical error.

A further observation concerns the variation in the temperature measurement due to the behavior of the flame. Observing the histogram of the data collected from 10,000 samples, two trends can be seen: around two different temperatures. This is due to the flame's fluctuations: initially, it will be very close to the thermocouple (which is fixed), so a higher temperature will be measured. As the combustion gases in the burner increase, the flame shrinks, moving away from the thermocouple, which will consequently measure a lower temperature. The residual graph illustrates this phenomenon very well.

Grafico dei residui della raccolta dati da 10000 campioni

1.3. Estimation of radiation losses

The temperature measurement indicated by a thermocouple is the sensor's own temperature, i.e., the hot junction. Generally, the indicated temperature will not coincide with the gas temperature, but will be affected by an error due to various factors (conduction and radiation errors).

Conductive losses can be neglected with a very good approximation if one considers that the ratio between the wire cross-section and their length must be as small as possible.

In the following analysis, only the thermocouple's radiative error will be considered.

Radiative losses can be estimated through the energy balance at the thermocouple's hot junction under steady-state conditions, therefore the thermal power entering through convective heat exchange with the hot gases must equal the net radiant power exchanged between the thermocouple and the surrounding environment:

$$h(T_{gas} - T_g) = \sigma\varepsilon(T_g^4 - T_a^4)$$

From this, the radiative loss of the thermocouple are:

$$\Delta T_{rad} = T_{gas} - T_g = \frac{\sigma\varepsilon(T_g^4 - T_a^4)}{h}$$

Where:

- $h \rightarrow$ convective heat transfer coefficient [W/m²K]
- $T_{gas} \rightarrow$ gas temperature [K]
- $\varepsilon \rightarrow$ thermocouple emissivity
- $\sigma \rightarrow$ Stefan-Boltzmann constant = $5.669 \cdot 10^{-8}$ [W/m²K⁴]
- $T_g \rightarrow$ junction temperature (temperature measured by the thermocouple) [K]
- $T_a \rightarrow$ ambient temperature (temperature of the walls of the room where the thermocouple is placed) [K]

Regarding the coefficient h , semi-empirical relationships can be used by considering the thermocouple junction as if it were a wire subjected to a high-temperature flow.

$$Nu = \frac{hD}{k} = C \cdot Re^n \cdot Pr^m$$

Where:

- $Nu \rightarrow$ dimensionless Nusselt number
- $D \rightarrow$ joint diameter
- $k \rightarrow$ thermal conductivity of the flow hitting the joint
- $Re \rightarrow$ Reynolds number $Re = VDv$
- $Pr \rightarrow$ Prandtl number
- C and n are coefficients that vary with the Reynolds number (in our case Re varies from 1 to 35, consequently $C=0.8$, $n=0.384$, and it will be considered $m \approx 0$)

Furthermore, the analysis will be carried out considering:

- Joint diameter: 0.35 mm
- Joint emissivity: 0.2
- Gas velocity: 5 m/s
- Hot air replaces the combustion gases, so the chemical-physical properties can be calculated as a function of temperature using the appropriate tables.
- Joint temperature equal to the average temperature resulting from the data collections before chapter (1.2) and subsequently chapter (1.3)

1.3.1. Joint temperature obtained from the first data collection (1600 samples)

The first data collection (from 1600 samples) provides an average joint temperature as follows:

$$T_g = T_{ave} = 1082.85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} = 1356 \text{ K}$$

From the air property tables, by interpolation, the kinematic diffusivity ν is obtained:

$$\nu = 195.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}$$

It is possible to calculate the Reynolds number, from which the Nusselt number is derived and consequently the convective heat transfer coefficient h :

$$Re = \frac{VD}{\nu} = \frac{5 \cdot 0.00035}{195.2 \cdot 10^{-6}} = 8.9652$$

$$Nu = C \cdot Re^n \cdot Pr^m = 1.8573$$

$$Nu = \frac{hD}{k} \rightarrow h = \frac{Nu \cdot k}{D} = \frac{1.8573 \cdot 0.0867}{0.00035} = 460.0797 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2\text{K}}$$

Where the thermal conductivity (k [WmK]) of the flow striking the thermocouple was obtained by interpolation from the air properties tables.

The thermocouple's radiation loss is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta T_{rad} = \frac{\sigma \epsilon (T_g^4 - T_a^4)}{h} = \frac{5.669 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot 0.2 \cdot (1356^4 - 320^4)}{460.0797} = 83.06 \text{ K}$$

Finally, you can determine the temperature of the gas:

$$\Delta T_{rad} = T_{gas} - T_g \rightarrow T_{gas} = \Delta T_{rad} + T_g = 1432.32 \text{ K}$$

1.3.2. Joint temperature obtained from the first data collection (10000 samples)

The second data collection (from 1000 samples) provides an average joint temperature as follows:

$$T_g = T_{ave} = 1159.17 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} = 1432.32 \text{ K}$$

In this case the kinematic diffusivity is:

$$\nu = 213.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}$$

The Reynolds number, the Nusselt number and the convective heat transfer coefficient h are calculated:

$$Re = \frac{VD}{\nu} = \frac{5 \cdot 0.00035}{213.1 \cdot 10^{-6}} = 8.2121$$

$$Nu = C \cdot Re^n \cdot Pr^m = 1.7957$$

$$Nu = \frac{hD}{k} \rightarrow h = \frac{Nu \cdot k}{D} = \frac{1.7957 \cdot 0.0909}{0.00035} = 466.3689 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2\text{K}}$$

Where the thermal conductivity (k) of the flow hitting the thermocouple was obtained by interpolation from the air properties tables.

The thermocouple's radiation loss is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta T_{rad} = \frac{\sigma \varepsilon (T_g^4 - T_a^4)}{h} = \frac{5.669 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot 0.2 \cdot (1432.32 - 320^4)}{466.3689} = 102.07 \text{ K}$$

Finally, you can determine the temperature of the gas:

$$\Delta T_{rad} = T_{gas} - T_g \rightarrow T_{gas} = \Delta T_{rad} + T_g = 1534.39 \text{ K}$$

1.3.3. Radiative Loss Analysis with Varying Gas Velocities

For the more realistic case in which the gas velocity is not constant but variable in the burner, it is possible to write the radiative loss ΔT_{rad} as a function of the gas velocity. In fact, it is a function of the convective heat transfer coefficient, which, through the Nusselt number, depends on the Reynolds number and therefore on the gas velocity.

Considering the relation

$$Nu = \frac{hD}{k} = C \cdot Re^n \cdot Pr^m$$

Since $Re \propto V$ then $h \propto V^n$ and consequently $\Delta T_{rad} \propto \frac{1}{V^n}$

In particular, considering a range of gas velocities in the burner from 5 m/s to 30 m/s, the radiative loss of the thermocouple takes on the trend shown in the graph in the figure.

It is evident that radiative loss decreases as velocity increases. This behavior is due to the fact that increasing velocity leads to an increase in the convective heat transfer coefficient, which therefore allows for better heat exchange between the gas and the thermocouple, limiting its radiative loss.

2. Test bench setup for a micro/cogeneration system

2.1. State of the art

2.1.1. Cogeneration (CHP) and micro-cogeneration

Cogeneration is defined as the combined production of electricity and heat, both intended as useful effects, with a cascade process.[1] Typically, for the sole production of electricity, thermodynamic cycles are used that release part of the energy entering the cycle into the environment in the form of high-temperature heat. The purpose of cogeneration is to exploit this heat, which would otherwise be wasted. Possible ways to use this energy source include boiling water, generating steam, or heating buildings. By minimizing waste, cogeneration plants generally convert 75-80% of the fuel source into usable energy (a much higher percentage compared to traditional systems, around 45%). This is not always enough to ensure that the combined production of thermal and electrical energy is, at least from an economic point of view, more advantageous than the separate one.

One of the main challenges is transporting heat to the user, which is accomplished via a fluid (energy carrier) placed in a heat exchanger through which high-temperature exhaust gases are passed. This process is only effective when our energy carrier has to travel relatively short distances, due to energy losses related to transport. Ultimately, to determine whether cogeneration is truly effective in reducing overall system costs, it is necessary to analyze not only the thermodynamic aspect but also the context in which it is used. Generally, it can be advantageous to implement it when the thermal energy demand is close to the power cycle plant; otherwise, separate generation of the two forms of energy may be even more advantageous, at least from an economic standpoint.

It is precisely in the market segment left untapped by cogeneration, based on large-scale plants and therefore with zero mobility, that micro-cogeneration fits in. Indeed, bigger does not always mean better, and this is precisely the essence of microturbines. As the name suggests, a microturbine is nothing more than the heart of a micro-cogeneration plant, which is legally defined as a unit with a maximum generation capacity of less than 50 kWe.[2]. The strong point of these plants is their almost zero transport losses. In fact, given the modest size of the plant, it can be installed without problems close to the thermal demand, furthermore the costs associated with a technology of this type are significantly reduced compared to those associated with much larger machines, making this solution accessible to a much wider spectrum of users.

2.1.2. Stirling Engine: Historical Notes and Operating Principle

Robert Stirling (Methven, October 25, 1790 – Galston, June 6, 1878), a Scottish Protestant pastor, was the inventor of the Stirling engine. He inherited his father's passion for engineering, but studied theology at university. Robert, along with his brother James, an engineer, filed several other patents for improvements to his Stirling engine. Concerned about the dangers posed to mine and foundry workers by steam engines, which frequently exploded due to the poor quality of the cast iron boilers available at the time, he decided to improve hot-air engines in the hope of providing a safer alternative. The innovative contribution of R. Stirling's patent was the introduction of a regenerator into the

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system. This device allowed both an increase in the engine's efficiency and operation at lower pressures, thus reducing the risk of explosions. The engine operates in a closed cycle using a gas as the thermodynamic fluid (usually air, nitrogen, or helium and hydrogen in high-efficiency versions). When the correct temperature difference between its hot and cold points is reached and the engine is started appropriately, a cyclic pulsation is triggered, which is transformed into an alternating motion by the pistons. The motion continues as long as the temperature difference remains constant, supplying heat to the hot point and removing it from the cold point. The Stirling engine requires little maintenance, and combustion is not restricted to specific fuels. [3]

Figura 1 – Rappresentazione ciclo e schema motore Stirling

2.1.3. Why Stirling engine?

Since micro-CHP systems are intended for installation in urban areas, one of the most important requirements they must meet is that of being low-polluting systems, even at the expense of improved performance. In this sense, the Stirling engine, being an external combustion cycle, features regular and continuous combustion capable of operating at an optimal stoichiometric ratio, thus drastically reducing pollutant emissions. Typically, a natural gas-fueled Stirling engine used in microgeneration can achieve an electrical efficiency of around 15%, which is not significantly lower than other technologies on the market. The critical aspects of this technology are mainly more complicated power control methods and higher investment costs.

2.2. Test bench setup

2.2.1. Micro-cogeneration system description

The microgeneration plant for which the test bench will be set up is the Whispergen EU1 model manufactured by EHE. The system is based on the Stirling cycle and is fueled by natural gas. It was designed to serve a domestic environment for heating and producing hot water.

Technical specifications released by the manufacturer [4]:

- Gross electrical power of 1 kW
- Electrical efficiency of 10-11%
- Rated thermal power of 7.5-8.3 kW
- Thermal efficiency greater than 85%
- Possibility of operating an auxiliary burner to reach 14.4 kW of thermal power

2.2.2. Test bench goals

The experimental test bench is to be set up with the following aims:

- characterise the system's behaviour by evaluating the following indices:
 - Electrical efficiency (η_{el})
 - Thermal efficiency (η_{th})
 - Electrical index (I_{el})
 - Energy saving index (IRE)
- analyse the condition and composition of the system's exhaust fumes

2.2.3. Choice of variables to measure

To characterize the system with the aforementioned indicators, it is necessary to select the variables that quantify energy expenditure or production. Energy expenditure is essentially represented by the use of natural fuel; therefore, it will be essential to measure the flow rate of natural gas entering the system and its composition to estimate an adequate LHV. Energy production, on the other hand, is dual: on the one hand, it will be necessary to measure the electrical power produced and, on the other, estimate the thermal power generated. The former can be measured by connecting directly to the electrical circuit served by our system, while to quantify the latter, it will be necessary to measure how much and how much water our system can heat. For this reason, the test bench will be equipped with a heat exchanger through which a flow of water (to be heated) and the flue gases (to be cooled) generated by the system will flow. Finally, considering that the system will be used primarily in urban environments, it was essential to ensure that, in addition to good energy savings, the system is compliant with, if not better than, the latest technologies available on the market in terms of pollution. The variables measured are:

- Natural gas flow rate
- Chemical composition of natural gas
- Electrical power generated
- Water flow rate in the hydraulic circuit
- Return water temperature
- Delivery water temperature
- Chemical composition of the fumes
- Temperature of the fumes.

Parameter	Value
Natural gas flow rate	15.395 NI/m
Electric power generated	0.954 kW
Water flow rate	0.201 kg/s
Return water temperature	45.03 °C
Discharge water temperature	55.06 °C
Flue gas temperature	50 °C

Natural gas components	X_{i,ng} [%]
CH ₄	89.40
C ₂ H ₆	5.00
C ₃ H ₈	1.10
C ₄ H ₁₀	0.30
C ₅ H ₁₂	0.06
C ₆ H ₁₄	0.04
N ₂	2.40
CO ₂	1.70

Fumes gas components	ppm
CO	20
SO ₂	0
NO ₂	1
NO	9
NO _x	10
CO ₂	7.8
O ₂	7

2.3. Measurement equipment

2.3.1. Premise on the data statistical analysis

First of all, it is assumed a uniform probability distribution to evaluate instrumental uncertainties, meaning no value has a greater probability of being output than the others. Therefore, once the instrument's accuracy is known (a value always provided by the manufacturer), the following formula will be used to estimate instrumental uncertainty:

$$u = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}}$$

Since accuracies are usually provided by manufacturers with a 95% confidence interval, it was not deemed necessary to extend the confidence interval.

2.3.2. Data acquisition module

Before discussing the choice of various measuring instruments, it is advisable to select a specific data acquisition system, since the uncertainty introduced by this instrument will affect every measurement performed. The criteria followed in evaluating the module that best suited the needs of the test bench were: a minimum number of acquisition channels equal to 8 (equal to the number of measured variables), high accuracy, and the ability to acquire physical quantities of various kinds. The maximum sampling frequency achievable by the instrument was not given particular importance because the system being analyzed is characterized by very long transients; consequently, it will not be necessary to acquire a large number of data points in close proximity. After careful evaluation, the “QuantumX MX840B” measurement module was selected, whose characteristics are in line with the needs of the test bench. This instrument is also excellent for its ability to amplify signals and for its high versatility, which makes it compatible with any other measurement system described below. The relevant parameters from the instrument's technical data sheet are shown in the table.

Model	Number of channels	Sampling frequency	Bit	Precision class
MX840B	8	40 kS/s	24	0.05-0.1

As a precaution, only the worst accuracy class certified by the manufacturer, i.e. accuracy class 0.1, will be considered.

$$Acc = 0.1\% \cdot X$$

$$u_{AD} = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}}$$

Figura 3 – Modulo di misura QuantumX MX840B

2.3.3. Electric power measurement

This parameter is of fundamental importance for calculating many of the indices, the estimation of which is one of the purposes of the test bench. It was therefore deemed important to invest in an instrument with high reliability. Also taking into account the interesting range of values (approximately 1 kW), the high-precision "Fluke Norma 4000" power analyzer was selected.

The instrument is chosen based on its full-scale value, so that it can measure the electrical power produced by the system without saturation errors, and above all because the instrument is characterized by an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$ of the measured value.[5] Note that in this case, the uncertainty in the electrical power is not affected by the imprecision of the acquisition system described in the previous paragraph because the instrument selected here also has a data acquisition function and therefore does not require the measurement module.

$$Acc = 0.1\% \cdot P_{el} = 0.954 W$$

$$u(P_{el}) = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}} = 0.551 W$$

$$u(P_{el})_{rel} = \frac{u(P_{el})}{P_{el}} = 5.78 \cdot 10^{-4}$$

Figura 4 – Fluke Norma 4000

2.3.4. Temperatures measurement

In the test bench illustrated above, three temperatures are measured: that of the exhaust gases and those of the supply and return water. The first is necessary for a complete description of the state of the flue gases, while the other two will be used to estimate the thermal power.

The three meters must meet more or less the same constraints: have a full scale compatible with the expected measurements (40-60°C) and be adequately waterproof (IP67/68).

Given these necessary premises, platinum resistance thermometers are chosen. Specifically Pt100. A Pt100 probe is a platinum resistance thermometer with a nominal resistance defined according to the IEC 751 (EN 60751) standard of 100 Ω at a temperature of 0°C.

This choice was made due to the following advantages:

- Wider temperature range from -200°C to 850°C
- Nearly linear characteristic curve
- Excellent precision
- Excellent interchangeability
- High and long-lasting stability

Figura 5 – Schema di una termoresistenza

Pt 100 resistance thermometers are divided into uncertainty classes, each characterized by an appropriate uncertainty range. The main classes are summarized in the following table.

(Where T refers to the temperature read by the resistance thermometer).

Uncertainty class	Uncertainty interval [°C]
AA	$\pm 0.1 + 0.0017T$
A	$\pm 0.15 + 0.002T$
B	$\pm 0.3 + 0.005T$
C	$\pm 0.6 + 0.01T$

Two RTDs belonging to different uncertainty classes are now compared and, consequently, different prices. The goal is to find the right technical-economic compromise, by evaluating whether the best price can justify a higher level of uncertainty. The two models considered are summarized in the following table [6] [7].

Manufacturer	IFM Electronic	TC Direct
Uncertainty class	A	B
Protection class	IP68	IP67
Operating range	-40°C to 150°C	-75°C to 250°C
Price	120€	40€

Since both probes meet the constraints imposed by our test bench in terms of operating range and water resistance, the next step is to evaluate the uncertainties introduced by the two instruments.

The inaccuracies in the water flow and return temperatures are considered more significant than those in the flue gas temperature. Therefore, only the total uncertainty in the ΔT of the circuit water will be analyzed, using an appropriate combination of uncertainties as a parameter to determine the best RTD from a technical and economic standpoint. Assuming a flow temperature of 55°C and a return temperature of 45°C (in complete agreement with the experimental data available to us), the results in terms of uncertainty and relative uncertainty for the two types of RTDs are summarized below.

Manufacturer	IFM Electronic	TC Direct
Uncertainty class	A	B
$u_{T_{w,in}}$	0.240°C	0.525°C
$u_{T_{w,out}}$	0.260°C	0.575°C
$u_{T_{w,in,rel}}$	0.53%	1.17%
$u_{T_{w,out,rel}}$	0.47%	1%

Since the parameter of interest is the temperature difference between the flow and return of the water, it is necessary to apply the combination of the uncertainties relating to the 2 temperatures:

$$\Delta T = T_{w,out} - T_{w,in} = 55 - 45 = 10^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$u_{\Delta T} = \sqrt{u_{T_{w,out}}^2 + u_{T_{w,in}}^2}$$

So the uncertainties related to the temperature difference for the two instruments are as follows:

Manufacturer	IFM Electronic	TC Direct
Uncertainty class	A	B
$u_{\Delta T}$	0.35°C	0.79°C

$u_{\Delta T,rel}$	3.5%	7.79%
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From the analysis of the combined uncertainty, it is clear that TC resistance thermometers are unusable given the high imprecision that their use entails on ΔT . It is therefore advisable to purchase sensors produced by ifm electronic for measuring water temperatures. Given the high relative uncertainty on ΔT , one might consider purchasing instruments with an even better uncertainty class (AA). In this case, however, it was decided to reserve a good budget for the purchase of a mass flow meter to be inserted into the hydraulic system, which can also provide us with a temperature measurement on the delivery water (as this introduces the greatest uncertainty on the ΔT measurement) with greater precision. By purchasing a single IFM Electronic sensor, the definitive conclusion of the discussion relating to temperature measurement is therefore postponed to the next chapter. Finally, you could also consider purchasing a CT instrument to measure flue gas temperature, accepting a relative uncertainty of approximately 1%. This measurement is more qualitatively important and offers cost savings. However, it is necessary to evaluate the uncertainty in the inlet and outlet temperatures introduced by the acquisition system:

$$Acc = 0.1\% \cdot T_{w,out} = 0.055^{\circ}C$$

$$u_{AD,Tw,out} = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}} = 0.032^{\circ}C$$

$$Acc = 0.1\% \cdot T_{w,in} = 0.045^{\circ}C$$

$$u_{AD,Tw,in} = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}} = 0.026^{\circ}C$$

$$u_{\Delta T,AD} = \sqrt{u_{AD,Tw,out}^2 + u_{AD,Tw,in}^2} = 0.041^{\circ}C$$

It is now possible to evaluate the combination of uncertainties of the temperature meters and the acquisition module as:

$$u_{\Delta T} = \sqrt{u_{AD}^2 + u_{Thermoresistance}^2} = 0.35^{\circ}C$$

2.3.5. Flows measurement

To perform this type of measurement, there are two main options: mass flow meters or volumetric flow meters. The main differences between the two, as usual, are cost and uncertainty. While mass flow meters (based on the Coriolis effect) are highly precise (uncertainties within a range of 0.1-0.05%) but also very expensive, volumetric flow meters

(the best ones exploit Faraday's law) have lower accuracy (due to the uncertainty in water density, on which the measurement depends heavily) but are less expensive.

Two such instruments will be installed in the test bench, one to measure the water flow rate in the hydraulic circuit and the other to measure the natural gas flow rate consumed by the system.

It is important that both measurements have low uncertainty, as they are fundamental parameters for calculating the various characteristic efficiencies of the system being analyzed. The choice therefore fell

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on mass flow meters both to minimize the level of uncertainty (at the expense of an undoubtedly higher cost) but also for other reasons discussed below. In the case of the water system, the possibility of installing a mass flow meter was suggested by the opportunity to have, in addition to a precise flow measurement, also an accurate measurement of the temperature of the branch in which the sensor will be installed. However, the choice for measuring fuel flow was almost inevitable, as it is impossible to use a volumetric flow meter because the conductivity of the material is lower than the minimum threshold required for these instruments to operate using Faraday's law. The use of volumetric flow meters that exploit other phenomena is not even considered because it would introduce excessively high uncertainties.

Since the two flow rates differ by more than an order of magnitude (approximately 0.8 kg/h for natural gas versus over 700 kg/h for water flow), it was necessary to select two different flow meter models.

For the hydraulic circuit meter, it was decided to turn to the manufacturer "Emerson," whose "Micro Motion Elite" series was deemed the most suitable. After carefully examining their catalog [8], the "CMFS025M" model was chosen, which has the following characteristics:

Model	Nominal flow	Maximum flow	Flow accuracy	Accuracy class
CMFS025M	1116 kg/h	2100 kg/h	±0,1%	A

This model was chosen for two key reasons: first, all models made with an expensive nickel alloy to withstand high temperatures were discarded. This is because our system, which operates at a maximum of 60-70°C, is perfectly adequate for the stainless steel of the selected model. Second, of all the steel instruments, it has the nominal range closest to the operating

range of our system. Finally, this instrument measures temperature with uncertainty class A; this allows us to purchase one less RTD without compromising measurement accuracy. It would be pointless to repeat the calculations, so it is decided to lower the cost of the test bench while maintaining a relative uncertainty in ΔT of 3.5%. The uncertainties are as follows:

- Uncertainty related to the flow meter:

$$Acc = 0.1\% \cdot \dot{m}_w = 2.01 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg/s}$$

$$u_{flow\ sensor}(\dot{m}_w) = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}} = 1.16 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg/s}$$

- Uncertainty related to the data acquisition module:

$$Acc = 0.1\% \cdot \dot{m}_w = 2.01 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg/s}$$

$$u_{AD}(\dot{m}_w) = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}} = 1.16 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg/s}$$

- Combined uncertainty

$$u_{\Delta T} = \sqrt{u_{AD}^2 + u_{flow\ sensor}^2} = 1.64 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg/s}$$

Figura 6 – Emerson Micro Motion ELITE

To perform the other measurement, the "IN-FLOW F-111-BI" model from Brokhorst was identified as the ideal instrument given the much smaller flow rate to be detected. This model was selected for two reasons: the first is that, given the gas pressure of 10 bar, it would be unnecessarily expensive to purchase an instrument that operates at much higher pressures. The F-111 model can operate up to a maximum pressure of 100 bar, the minimum available in the Brokhorst catalog. The second reason for selecting this model is that, since all the

instruments in the catalog are affected by full-scale errors, it is decided to select the instrument with the minimum full-scale that would meet our needs.

Model	Minimum flow range	Maximum flow range	Accuracy
F-111-BI	0.16-8 NI/min	0.16-25 NI/min	±0,5% Rd plus ±0,1% FS

Similarly to the previous case, the uncertainties are calculated:

- Uncertainty related to the flow meter:

$$Acc = 0,5\% \cdot 15,395 + 0,1\% \cdot 25 = 0,102 \text{ NI/min}$$

$$u_{gas \text{ flow meter}}(\dot{v}_{gn}) = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}} = 0.0589 \text{ NI/min}$$

- Uncertainty related to the data acquisition module:

$$Acc = 0.1\% \cdot 15.395 = 0.015395 \text{ NI/min}$$

$$u_{AD}(\dot{v}_{gn}) = \frac{Acc}{\sqrt{3}} = 8.89 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ NI/min}$$

- Combined uncertainty

$$u_{\Delta T} = \sqrt{u_{AD}^2 + u_{gas \text{ flow sensor}}^2} = 0.0596 \text{ NI/min}$$

Figura 7 – Bronkhorst IN-FLOW

2.3.6. Identification of the chemical composition of natural gas and exhaust fumes

To achieve a highly accurate energy balance, the test bench was equipped with a gas chromatograph. This instrument will allow for precise knowledge of the composition of the

natural gas used to power the machine. Another equally important application will be to detect the presence of potentially abnormal quantities of pollutants in exhaust fumes, allowing for a qualitative description of the plant's environmental impact.

The guiding criteria for choosing this instrument were versatility—that is, the ability to analyze both the gas mixture present in the fuel and the flue gases without problems—and a low repeatability standard deviation, allowing for multiple samples to be taken at different points during the machine's operation with highly reliable results. The company "INFICON" was contacted, and the model chosen was the "3000 Micro GC." This machine is capable of analyzing all substances of interest, detecting a wide range of hydrocarbons (C1-C6) and other gases such as O₂, N₂, CO, and CO₂. It is also equipped with 4 channels that work independently, allowing a single machine to simultaneously acquire an analysis of the two mixtures.

The manufacturer certifies a relative standard deviation of less than 1% for each component of the mixture [10][11]. To be safe, it is advisable to consider this uncertainty value when analyzing the available data.

Figura 7 – INFICON 3000 Micro GC

2.4. Calculation of the cycle parameters of interest

2.4.1. LHV calculation, heat input (Q_{in}) and useful thermal power (Q_{out})

To evaluate the performance and efficiency of the cycle being studied, it is necessary to know the lower heating value (LHV) of the fuel used and its mass flow rate. It is useful to construct the following table to evaluate the lower heating value:

Natural gas components	Chemical composition	Molecular mass (MM_i) [$kg_x/kmol_x$]	LHV [$MJ/kmol$]	Mole fraction (x_i) [$kmol_x/kmol_{gn}$]
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Methan	CH ₄	16.04	802.34	0.894
Ethane	C ₂ H ₆	30.07	1437.2	0.05
Propane	C ₃ H ₈	44.1	2044.2	0.011
Butane	C ₄ H ₁₀	58.12	2659.3	0.003
Pentane	C ₅ H ₁₂	72.15	3272.6	0.0006
Hexane	C ₆ H ₁₄	86.17	3856.7	0.0004
Nitrogen	N ₂	28.01	/	0.0240
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂	44.01	/	0.017

Nitrogen (N₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) are ignored in the LHV calculation because they are inert gases and therefore do not react in the combustion process.

The molar mass of natural gas is:

$$MM_{gn} = \sum_{i=1}^8 MM_i \cdot x_i = 18 \text{ kg/kmol}$$

Now the PCI is determined using the formula:

$$PCI_{gn} = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^6 LHV_i \cdot x_i)}{MM_{gn}} = 45.73 \text{ MJ/kg}$$

To calculate the incoming heat Q_{in} in kW, you need to know the mass flow rate of the natural gas (in kg/s). From the data in the previous chapter $\dot{m} = 15.395 \text{ Nl/min}$. Thanks to some simple conversions:

$$\dot{m}_{gn} = \frac{15,395 \text{ Nl/min}}{1000 \text{ Nl/Nm}^3} \cdot \frac{1}{122,413 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{kmole}} \cdot 18 \text{ kg/Kmole} = 2,06 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg/s}$$

Consequently:

$$Q_{in} = \dot{m}_{gn} \cdot LHV_{gn} = 9420 \text{ kW}$$

It is now possible to obtain the useful thermal power in kW, knowing the temperature difference between flow and return and the water flow rate in the hydraulic circuit (0.201 kg/s) (both from chapter 2.3.3):

$$Q_{out} = \dot{m}_{H_2O} c_p \Delta T = 0.201 \cdot 4.186 \cdot 10 = 8.414 \text{ kW}$$

2.4.2. Efficiencies and performance indicators

The definition of "efficiency" for a cogeneration system is not straightforward, since, for each energy expenditure, there are two useful effects, which have different thermodynamic and economic values and can be "weighted" differently. First, the indices are defined, which are

parameters that take into account only two of the three energy flows and therefore cannot be considered "efficiencies" in the strict sense. These are:

- Electric efficiency

$$\eta_{el} = \frac{P_{el}}{Q_{in}} = \frac{P_{el}}{m_{gn} \cdot LHV_{gn}} = \frac{0.954}{9.420} = 0.1013 = 10.13\%$$

- Thermal efficiency

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{Q_{out}}{Q_{in}} = \frac{8.414}{9.420} = 0.8932 = 89.32\%$$

- Electrical index

$$I_E = \frac{P_{el}}{Q_{out}} = \frac{0.954}{8.414} = 0.1134 = 11.34\%$$

To account for both useful effects, it would be necessary to define a "first-principle efficiency." However, this efficiency would have the flaw of assigning the same value to electricity and heat, an approach that is flawed from both an energy and economic perspective.

To evaluate the two goods produced differently, it would be possible to refer to a "second-principle efficiency," which, however, would highlight the opposite problem: assigning too low a value to useful heat.

Consequently, to express the quality of a cogeneration operation with a single index, it is advisable to compare the energy consumption of the cogeneration plant with that which would be achieved by producing the same goods without cogeneration.

In this regard, reference is made to the legislation currently in force (Ministerial Decree of August 4, 2011, following 2004/8/EC) which refers to the Primary Energy Index (PES), which corresponds to the Energy Savings Index (IRE):

$$PES = 1 - \frac{1}{\frac{\eta_{el}}{\eta_{el,c}} + \frac{\eta_{th}}{\eta_{th,c}}}$$

Where the efficiencies $\eta_{el,c}$ and $\eta_{th,c}$ are the efficiencies of the power plant and the boiler, respectively, with which the electrical power W and the thermal power Q_{out} would have been produced with conventional processes. [1]

These efficiencies are always defined by the legislation (Ministerial Decree of 4 August 2011) and for a power plant and a boiler, both powered by natural gas (which is the fuel used by the micro-cogenerator being analyzed), they apply:

$$\eta_{el,c} = 0.500$$

$$\eta_{th,c} = 0.89$$

Therefore, the Primary Energy Saving index is:

$$PES = 1 - \frac{1}{\frac{0.101}{0.500} + \frac{0.893}{0.890}} = 0.170$$

2.4.3. Evaluation of combined uncertainties

One of the parameters observed in selecting measuring instruments was the uncertainty they introduce. Precisely because they are characterized by a systematic error, this affects the quantities calculated directly or indirectly from the values obtained with the selected instruments. It is therefore necessary to define the measurements of these quantities with the associated uncertainties.

Now the analysis proceeds with calculating the uncertainties of the various parameters previously calculated, starting with the uncertainty of the LHV, which influences the uncertainty of the input heat and then all subsequent ones.

$$u_{LHV} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^6 \left(\frac{LHV_i}{MM_i} u_{x_i} \right)^2}$$

Where:

$$u_{x_i} = x_i \cdot 0.01 + x_i \cdot \frac{0.1\%}{\sqrt{3}}$$

Note that the coefficient 0.01 (1%) in the first of the last two equations is the uncertainty of the gas chromatograph.

Then the uncertainty of the lower heating value is:

$$u_{LHV} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^6 \left(\frac{LHV_i}{MM_i} u_{x_i} \right)^2} = 0.45 \text{ MJ/kg}$$

For the calculations to come, the calculation of relative uncertainty is useful:

$$\frac{u_{LHV}}{LHV} = 0.00984$$

The relative and absolute uncertainties are now calculated:

$$\frac{u_{Q_{in}}}{Q_{in}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u_{LHV}}{LHV} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{m_{gn}}}{m_{gn}} \right)^2} = 0.0105 = 1.05\%$$

$$u_{Q_{in}} = 0.0105 \cdot Q_{in} = 0.1 \text{ kW}$$

$$\frac{u_{Q_{out}}}{Q_{out}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u_{\Delta T}}{\Delta T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{m_{H2O}}}{m_{H2O}} \right)^2} = 0.035 = 3.5\%$$

$$u_{Q_{out}} = 0.035 \cdot Q_{out} = 0.29 \text{ kW}$$

Remembering that $u_{Pel}=0.000577$ $P_{el}=0.00055$ kW:

$$\frac{u_{I_E}}{I_E} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u_{Pel}}{P_{el}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{Qout}}{Q_{out}}\right)^2} = 0.0035 = 3.5\%$$

$$u_{I_E} = 0.0105 \cdot I_E = 0.004 = 0.40\%$$

$$\frac{u_{\eta_{el}}}{\eta_{el}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u_{Pel}}{P_{el}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{Qin}}{Q_{in}}\right)^2} = 0.00105 = 1.05\%$$

$$u_{\eta_{el}} = 0.00105 \cdot \eta_{el} = 0.0011 = 0.11\%$$

$$\frac{u_{\eta_{th}}}{\eta_{th}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u_{Qout}}{Q_{out}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{Qin}}{Q_{in}}\right)^2} = 0.0365 = 3.65\%$$

$$u_{\eta_{th}} = 0.0365 \cdot \eta_{th} = 0.033 = 3.3\%$$

$$u_{PES} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial PES}{\partial \eta_{th}} u_{\eta_{th}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial PES}{\partial \eta_{el}} u_{\eta_{el}}\right)^2} = 0.026$$

To summarize, the measurements of all the quantities of interest are:

- $LHV = 45,73 \pm 0,45$ MJ/kg
- $Q_{in} = 9,42 \pm 0,10$ kW
- $Q_{out} = 8,41 \pm 0,29$ kW
- $I_E = 0,1134 \pm 0,0040$
- $\eta_{el} = 10,13 \pm 0,11$ %
- $\eta_{th} = 89,32 \pm 0,33$ %
- $PES = 0,170 \pm 0,026$

2.5. Conclusion

As predicted, from an analysis of the various calculated efficiencies, it's possible to conclude that a Stirling cycle cogeneration system is an excellent way to produce domestic hot water for residential or industrial use (the high thermal efficiency is proof of this). The indicators describing the quality of electricity production are also unsurprising, remaining at reasonable levels. These parameters will certainly need to be improved in the future to make Stirling cycle micro-CHP systems more competitive on the market.

As a final indicator, the PES is analyzed, which is the most significant parameter for determining the quality of cogeneration systems. To evaluate this index, it is necessary to refer to the conditions set by Directive 2004/8/EC to obtain the qualification of "high-efficiency cogeneration" (and to benefit from certain incentives and benefits) that are easily determined:

- PES ≥ 0 for electrical power less than 1 MW
- PES ≥ 0.1 for electrical power greater than or equal to 1 MW. [12]

The analyzed test bench certifies a PES certainly greater than 0 (even considering the very high uncertainty of the calculation), placing the Whispergen system among those systems that effectively allow fuel savings compared to traditional technologies.

Ultimately, the Whispergen lends itself as an excellent alternative to domestic boilers, allowing the production of hot water with the same efficiency as traditional technologies but with the advantage of simultaneously producing electrical power.

The second purpose of the test bench was to perform a qualitative analysis of the fumes discharged into the environment at the end of the process. Please note that the results obtained via gas chromatography are reported in the table in chapter 2.2.5.

Further confirmation of excellent thermal efficiency is the very low flue gas temperature (50°C), which indicates that very little energy is dissipated into the environment, optimizing primary energy consumption.

The pollutants resulting from combustion are primarily unburned, particularly carbon and nitrogen oxides.

To draw conclusions, it is useful to compare the pollutant concentrations of our system with those of other well-established systems on the market. [4]

Pollutants	Conventional natural gas boiler	Conventional natural gas boiler	Whispergen
CO	0.04 kg/MWh	0.08 kg/MWh	0.0357 kg/MWh
NO _x	0.21 kg/MWh	0.29 kg/MWh	0.0293 kg/MWh

The analysis thus shows CO emissions comparable to those of natural gas-fired boilers and halved compared to those fired by diesel.

The best result concerns NO_x emissions, which are drastically reduced compared to other systems, placing the Whispergen in the so-called "eco-friendly" boiler category.

To extend the results obtained from the test bench presented in the paper, it will be compared with other similar systems. In the degree thesis "Setup of a microcogeneration laboratory (LMC) and tests on a PEM-FC system" (A. Cacace, 2009-2010) [13], in which a similar test bench was used to analyze electrical and thermal efficiency, relative uncertainties of approximately 3.7% for the former and 3.6% for the latter were obtained. Relative uncertainties of approximately 3% were also found in other works. The test bench set up in the paper can therefore be considered in line, in terms of precision and reliability, with other systems already on the market. Therefore, it can be considered suitable not only for testing the Whispergen system under consideration, but also for testing other models and cogeneration systems.

In conclusion, analyzing the measurement uncertainties, it can be hypothesized that a future investment to improve the test bench could certainly be the purchase of resistance thermometers for measuring the flow and return water temperature with a higher uncertainty class, given that these measurements are the greatest source of inaccuracy in the calculations. The choice of uncertainty class in this case is mandatory, given that the instruments selected are Class A, second only to Class AA in accuracy.

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